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Impact of Urban Flooding on Residential Property Investment in Rumuokwachi Community, Obio/Akpo Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Urban flooding poses a significant threat to residential property investments, particularly in rapidly urbanizing regions with inadequate drainage infrastructure. This study examines the impact of urban flooding on residential property investments in Rumuokwachi Community, Obioakpor Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria. A survey research design was adopted due to its effectiveness in capturing a representative sample and facilitating generalization. Primary data were collected through structured questionnaires administered to household heads and rent payers, while secondary data from books and online resources supplemented the study. The study employed simple random sampling technique to select 332 respondent's household residents determined using Slovin's formula at a 5% precision level. from a total number of 1961 residential buildings mapped out using Geographic Information System (GIS) tool and to distribute the questionnaire within the study area. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistical techniques via the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The study identifies excessive rainfall, poor drainage, sea-level rise, improper waste disposal, and rapid urbanization as major causes of flooding in Rumuokwachi. The findings indicate that prolonged retention of floodwater, lasting between 2 to 4 days, exacerbates property damage and poses significant health risks. Additionally, flooding adversely impacts residential property investments by lowering property values, reducing demand, increasing insurance costs, and hindering development projects. The study recommends flood mitigation strategies such as constructing flood protection embankments, improving drainage systems, raising public awareness, enforcing zoning regulations, and promoting investments in non-flood-prone areas. It also suggests implementing green infrastructure, desilting drainage systems, upgrading infrastructure in flood-prone areas, and adopting a comprehensive approach with regulatory reforms and community involvement.

Keywords: Urban Flooding, Residential Property Investment, Flood Mitigation, Rumuokwachi Community, Rivers State.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Urban flooding has become a significant challenge in many cities worldwide, particularly in developing countries where rapid urbanization, poor drainage systems, and inadequate land-use planning exacerbate the problem (Adelekan, 2022). Every year, millions of people are forcibly displaced from their homes, communities, cultures, livelihoods, and economies due to human-induced or natural disasters around the world. These disasters can take various forms, including floods, earthquakes, hurricanes, typhoons, wildfires, and landslides, all of which can cause widespread socio-economic disruption. They lead to devastation, death, injury, property damage, and emotional suffering. Disasters occur with varying speeds and magnitudes, but they can result in profound and unquantifiable losses to the elements at risk (Ogbanga, 2015).

Flooding, in particular, is a significant environmental crisis faced globally. According to Odunuga, Oyebande, and Omojola (2012), flooding is a serious disaster that not only causes extensive damage but also disrupts normal life and working conditions. Several reports indicate that thousands of lives have been lost, along with property worth billions, in various affected areas in Lagos, Nigeria (Emordi, 2012). Furthermore, the World Health Organization (WHO) states that flooding accounts for 40% of all natural disasters worldwide. The primary health impacts of flooding include deaths, injuries, waterborne diseases, and emotional trauma, which can occur during the flood event itself, during the recovery process, or as a result of damage to essential infrastructure, leading to the displacement of populations. On average, greater water depth and higher flow velocity during a flood lead to increased damage to property (Gayelord, 2008). Urban flooding occurs when excessive rainfall overwhelms drainage systems or when poor urban planning results in water accumulation in residential areas (Adeagbo, Olalekan, and Adetayo, 2021). The increasing frequency of floods in Rumuokwachi has raised concerns among property investors, homeowners, and government agencies regarding its long-term effects on real estate investments. Studies indicate that persistent flooding reduces property desirability, leading to lower rental yields and declining market values (Egbenta and Okwu, 2023). Additionally, the cost of maintaining flood-prone properties often discourages potential investors, thereby slowing down housing development and economic growth in affected areas (Nkwunonwo, Whitworth, and Billa., 2022).

In Nigeria, the situation regarding flooding mirrors trends observed globally. Flooding displaces more people than any other type of disaster, largely because approximately 20 percent of the Nigerian population is at risk of flooding (Etuonovbe, 2011). As a result, flooding is a persistent issue in Nigeria, consistently leading to loss of life and the displacement of communities. For example, in 2010, flooding resulted in the deaths of approximately 1,555 people and displaced around 258,000 others (Babatunde, 2011). Similarly, in 2012, floods claimed 361 lives and displaced 2.1 million individuals (Tokunbo and Ezigbo, 2012). Research conducted outside Nigeria has found that real estate properties located in designated floodplains are valued less than comparable properties situated outside these areas. In Australia, the value of such properties is typically lower by 4–12% (Lambley and Cordery, 2013), while in the UK, the reduction ranges from 15–35% (Lamond, 2008). In North Carolina, the average decrease is around 5.8% (Bin and Polasky, 2003), and in Japan, the decline in value is between 1.27% and 4.7% (Fukozono and Ikeda, 2003). However, in Nigeria, the negative impact of flooding on land and property values has often been assumed without a clear understanding of the degree of variability and impact.

Rumukwachi community in Obiakpo local government area of Rivers State has recorded series of flooding events in recent times. On the 9th of July 2020, a ravaging flood which destroyed properties and forced many to flee their homes in the community. Some residents while narrating their ordeal said the flood disaster has rendered them homeless and making life unbearable (Nkoli Omohud 2020). Similarly, the Rumukwachi - Ozuoba link Road in Obioakpo local government area in Rivers State was also taken over by flood as many electricity Poles were destroyed by the heavy downpour in the early hours of April 2nd, 2013. The flood which made the road inaccessible, paralyzed all economic activities around the area. The community development committee chairman (CDC) of the community said that many of the residents of the area had abandoned their homes for the fear of possible loss of life and prosperity. (Vanguard News April 2, 2013).

Several factors contribute to urban flooding in Rumuokwachi, including poor waste management, blocked drainage systems, land reclamation, and inadequate flood control measures. The rapid expansion of residential properties without adequate urban planning has further worsened the situation (Ogunbode and Ifegbesan, 2023). Moreover, climate change-induced extreme weather events have increased rainfall intensity, exacerbating flood risks in urban centers (Ajibade McBean, and Bezner-Kerr, 2021). These challenges necessitate urgent interventions to mitigate the adverse effects of flooding on residential property investments.

Despite government efforts to address urban flooding through infrastructural development and policy initiatives, the effectiveness of these measures remains questionable. Many property investors continue to experience financial losses due to flood-related damages, while tenants struggle with deteriorating living conditions (Okonkwo Eze, and Mba, 2023). Given the critical role of residential property investment in driving local economic development and providing housing solutions, the impact of urban flooding cannot be overlooked. The persistent risk of flooding has prompted a cautious approach among investors, who may either delay or withdraw from real estate projects in the area, thereby stalling urban growth and development (Okonkwo, Eze, and Mba, 2023). As a result, understanding the extent to which urban flooding affects residential property investment in Rumuokwachi is crucial for policymakers, investors, and urban planners. This study, therefore, seeks to evaluate the impact of urban flooding on residential property investment in Rumuokwachi Community, with a focus on identifying causes of flooding, assessing investor responses, and proposing strategies for flood risk mitigation.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Concept of Urban Flooding

The term "flood" unequivocally refers to the partial or complete inundation of normally dry land due to a rapid and unusual accumulation of surface water runoff from various sources or the overflow of inland or tidal waters (Amangabara and Gobo, 2010). Flooding is a well-defined temporary condition characterized by the inundation of typically dry areas, driven by either the overflow of inland or tidal waters or a significant and swift buildup of runoff (Jeb and Aggarwal, 2008). Urban flooding is a phenomenon that occurs when excessive rainfall, poor drainage systems, and unplanned urban expansion result in water accumulation beyond normal levels, leading to inundation of residential and commercial areas (Adelekan, 2022). Unlike riverine or coastal flooding, urban flooding is often driven by anthropogenic factors such as inadequate stormwater management, blocked drainage channels, and land-use changes (Nkwunonwo et al., 2022). This type of flooding significantly disrupts socio-economic activities, damages infrastructure, and reduces the liveability of affected areas. Flooding results in the loss of lives and property, and it can also lead to significant economic setbacks, particularly in developing countries (UNDP, 2015). It is a natural disaster that occurs due to heavy rainfall, which causes rivers to overflow their banks. Floods typically happen in low-lying areas, such as the bottom of valleys and coastal regions.

2.2 Concept of Residential Property Investment

Residential property investment involves the allocation of financial resources to acquire and develop housing units for rental income or capital appreciation (Olanrewaju et al., 2023). Investors consider factors such as location, infrastructure, demand trends, and environmental risks when making investment decisions. However, the exposure of properties to flooding risk introduces uncertainties that influence investor confidence and property market dynamics (Okonkwo et al., 2023). Flood-prone areas often experience property devaluation, lower rental yields, and increased maintenance costs, making them less attractive for investment (Nkwunonwo et al., 2022). Consequently, urban flooding affects the supply-demand equilibrium in the residential property market, as potential buyers and tenants avoid high-risk locations (Adeagbo et al., 2021).

2.3 Causes of Flooding

Flooding results in loss of life and property and can lead to severe economic setbacks, particularly in developing countries (UNDP, 2015). It is a natural disaster caused by heavy rainfall that leads to the overflow of riverbanks, often occurring in valley bottoms and coastal areas. Flooding is a global issue,

with various causes that depend on geographical, environmental, and human factors. According to Tabiri (2015), urban flooding primarily stems from negligence or ignorance, poor city planning, construction on waterways, and indiscriminate waste disposal. A study by Komolafe, Adegboyega, and Akinluyi (2015) reviewed flood risk in Nigeria, drawing insights from prior scholarly works and secondary data sources. They identified several key contributors to flooding in Nigeria, including high vulnerability levels, limited coping capacity among residents, and the increasing frequency of extreme weather events linked to climate change. Their research also highlighted poor urban planning and management as exacerbating factors.

In their examination of flooding and flood risk reduction strategies in Nigeria, Nkwunonwo, Whitworth, and Baily (2015) emphasized the recurrent nature of flood hazards. They identified rapid population growth, urbanization, inadequate urban planning, and climate change—specifically the increased frequency and intensity of rainfall—as major drivers of urban flooding. Similarly, Magami, Yahaya, and Mohammed (2014) assessed the causes and consequences of flooding in Nigeria, attributing it to factors such as dam failures, river overflow, coastal storms, non-compliance with meteorological warnings, delays in the evacuation of flood victims, and settlement in flood-prone areas. They also noted that heavy rainfall, the continuous release of excess water from artificial reservoirs, poor maintenance of drainage systems, and indiscriminate waste disposal further contribute to flooding events.

Additionally, Nwigwe and Embergo (2014) examined the causes and effects of flooding in Nigeria, revealing that illegal structures across drainage channels, land reclamation, poor physical planning, inadequate drainage infrastructure, blocked canals and drains, collapsed dams, and the nature of the terrain are significant factors in flood incidents in major cities and towns. Olajuyigbe, Rotowa, and Durojoye (2012) assessed flood hazards in Lagos, identifying high river levels, excessive surface runoff from heavy rainfall, insufficient drainage capacity, and obstruction of waterways as primary contributors to flooding. They also noted that the narrowing of river channels and the construction of residential and commercial developments in flood-prone areas significantly increase flood risks. Overall, the literature indicates that flooding in Nigeria is heavily influenced by a combination of human-induced and natural factors, with climate change, poor urban planning, and inadequate waste management playing critical roles.

Several other factors that contribute to urban flooding, particularly in developing regions, as identified in the literature include:

1. Rapid Urbanization and Unplanned Development – The expansion of cities without adequate infrastructure planning reduces permeable surfaces, leading to increased surface runoff (Adelekan, 2022).
2. Inadequate Drainage Systems – Poorly designed and clogged drainage networks hinder water flow, resulting in localized flooding (Nkwunonwo et al., 2022).
3. Climate Change and Extreme Weather Events – Increased rainfall intensity due to climate change has led to more frequent and severe urban floods. Additionally, rising sea levels and storm surges contribute to urban inundation, particularly in coastal cities (IPCC, 2021).
4. Poor Waste Management – Illegal waste dumping into drainage systems obstructs water flow, increasing flood risks. Furthermore, a lack of proper waste disposal facilities exacerbates environmental degradation (Ogunbode and Ifegbesan, 2023).
5. Topographical and Geological Factors – Low-lying urban areas are naturally prone to flooding due to inadequate natural drainage. Soil composition also plays a role, as highly compacted urban soils reduce infiltration capacity (Egbenta and Okwu, 2023).

2.4 The Impact of Urban Flooding on Real Estate Investment

Numerous studies have examined how flooding impacts property values in different countries. Bin and Polasky (2004) utilized Hurricane Floyd, which struck in 1999, as a natural experiment to analyze property prices for 8,375 homes from 1992 to 2002. Their findings showed that homes located within floodplains were, on average, valued 5.7% lower than similar properties situated outside flood-prone areas. This price discount doubled after Hurricane Floyd. Similarly, research conducted in Pennsylvania, California, and Illinois found that property prices declined following flood events but eventually

recovered to, or even exceeded, pre-flood levels. The recovery period was shorter in areas that experienced less severe flooding (Tobin and Montz, 1994). Overall, urban flooding impacts real estate investments in several significant ways:

2.4.1 Reduction in Property Values

The occurrence of severe or frequent flooding events in urban areas often leads to a decline in property values. Properties located in flood-prone areas are typically less appealing to potential buyers and tenants due to worries about property damage, safety risks, and higher insurance costs (Adelekan, 2022). Over time, these areas are likely to experience a sustained decrease in property values, as the risks associated with flooding outweigh the benefits of living in or investing in these locations. For instance, properties in Rumuokwachi and other coastal regions of Rivers State are at risk of long-term depreciation, considering that the threat of flooding overshadows the economic potential of these areas (Egbenta and Okwu, 2023).

2.4.2 Increased Risk Premiums and Insurance Costs

Property owners and real estate investors in flood-prone areas often face significantly higher insurance premiums, as insurers adjust their rates based on flood risk assessments. This increase in operational costs reduces overall profitability for landlords (Nkwunonwo et al., 2022). In regions with severe flood risks, flood insurance may be either unavailable or prohibitively expensive, forcing property owners to shoulder the full financial burden of flood-related damages. This uncertainty in insurance coverage discourages potential investors from committing to properties in such locations (Adelekan, 2022).

2.4.3 Impact on Rental Income and Occupancy Rates

Properties located in flood-prone areas often face lower rental demand. Tenants generally avoid these regions due to concerns about safety and potential property damage. As a result, property owners may have difficulty attracting tenants, leading to extended vacancies and decreased rental income (Ogunbode and Ifegbesan, 2023). After major flood events, properties in these areas typically experience even lower occupancy rates. High vacancy rates can deter investors since stable occupancy is essential for ensuring consistent returns on investment (Douglas et al., 2021).

2.4.4 Disruption of Development and Construction Projects

Urban flooding can cause delays or interruptions in construction and development projects, especially in areas prone to flooding. Heavy rainfall and flooding can damage construction materials and hinder site preparation, resulting in increased costs and extended timelines for real estate developers (Egbenta and Okwu, 2023). To mitigate flood risks, developers and investors may shift their focus toward higher-elevation areas or locations with lower vulnerability to flooding. Additionally, implementing flood mitigation measures, such as constructing elevated buildings or enhancing drainage systems, can significantly raise construction costs, which may further deter development in flood-prone regions (Nkwunonwo et al., 2022).

2.4.5 Long-Term Sustainability Concerns

Urban flooding poses significant long-term sustainability challenges for real estate investments, especially in rapidly growing cities like Port Harcourt, where urban expansion encroaches upon flood-prone areas. If flooding continues or worsens, the development of real estate and the expansion of infrastructure may be impeded, limiting the sector's growth potential (Ajibade, McBean, and Bezner-Kerr, 2021). Additionally, flooding causes environmental degradation, including the contamination of water sources and the destruction of green spaces, leading to deteriorating living conditions that diminish the appeal of real estate markets. Long-term health issues, such as waterborne diseases, further threaten the viability of real estate investments in flood-prone regions (Ogunbode and Ifegbesan, 2023).

From the literature, it is clear that urban flooding significantly affects real estate investment by reducing property values, increasing insurance costs, diminishing rental income, disrupting development projects, and raising long-term sustainability concerns. These challenges necessitate comprehensive flood mitigation strategies and informed investment decisions to safeguard the real estate sector from climate-related risks.

2.5 Mitigation Measures and Investment Opportunities

While urban flooding poses significant risks, literature by Douglas et al., (2021); Egbenta and Okwu, (2023); and Ogunbode and Ifegbesan, (2023) has documented several strategies and investment

opportunities that can help reduce negative impacts and promote sustainable real estate development in flood-prone areas such as:

- i) **Green Infrastructure:** Investing in green infrastructure, such as permeable pavements, green roofs, and bioswales, can effectively manage stormwater and decrease flooding risks. Developers who incorporate these features into their projects may see increased demand from environmentally conscious buyers or tenants (Douglas et al., 2021).
- ii) **Flood Protection Measures:** Developers can integrate flood protection features like raised foundations, flood barriers, and improved drainage systems to minimize property vulnerability to flooding. Such investments can provide a competitive edge in the market (Ajibade et al., 2021).
- iii) **Zoning and Land-Use Policies:** Governments can establish zoning regulations to restrict development in high-risk flood zones or to incentivize flood-resilient projects. Financial incentives, such as tax breaks or subsidies for developers building flood-resistant properties, can encourage more sustainable urban growth (Egbenta and Okwu, 2023).
- iv) **Early Warning Systems and Emergency Planning:** Real estate developers and investors can collaborate with local authorities to enhance early warning systems and emergency response plans, ensuring better preparedness for flood events. This approach can reduce the financial and social impacts of flooding and bolster investor confidence (Adelekan, 2022).
- v) **Diversification into Non-Flood-Prone Areas:** Investors can decrease their exposure to flood risks by diversifying their real estate portfolios to include properties in areas with lower flood risks. This strategy balances the hazards of investing in flood-prone regions with more stable and profitable ventures in safer locations (Nkwunonwo et al., 2022).
- vi) **Renewed Focus on Redevelopment:** Urban renewal projects that target flood-prone yet historically significant areas can create new investment opportunities. These redevelopment initiatives can revitalize affected neighborhoods while integrating flood mitigation strategies (Ogunbode, and Ifegbesan, 2023).

3.0 Study Area

The study will focus on the Rumuokwachi Community, located in the Obioakpor Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. This community is part of the larger Port Harcourt metropolis, situated between Latitude 4°45'N and 4°55'N, and Longitude 6°55'E and 7°05'E. Port Harcourt, a major city in the Niger Delta region, is positioned at the mouth of the Bonny River, approximately 25 km from the Atlantic Ocean. It is bordered by the Dockyard Creek/Bonny River and the Amadi Creek and has an average elevation of about 12 meters above sea level.

The Port Harcourt metropolis spans two local government areas: Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor. It experiences a tropical climate characterized by distinct dry and rainy seasons. The city's temperatures remain consistently high, with a mean maximum of approximately 34°C and a mean minimum of around 21°C. The highest temperatures are typically recorded between April and October.

Rumuokwachi Community is particularly vulnerable to frequent flooding due to inadequate drainage infrastructure, changing rainfall patterns, and rapid urbanization. Analyzing the impact of urban flooding on residential property investment in this community will provide critical insights into the broader implications of flood risks in similar urban centers across Nigeria.

Figure 3.1: Topographic Map showing the study area Rumukwachi, Obio Akpor, R/S
 Source: Urban and Regional GIS Lab, Rivers State University, 2024.

4.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed a survey research design to evaluate the impact of urban flooding on residential property investment in Rumuokwachi Community, Obioakpor Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria. The survey research design was selected due to its efficiency in making generalizations from a sampled population and its cost-effectiveness in data collection (Creswell, 2014; Fowler, 2009). The study relied primarily on primary data obtained through structured questionnaires administered to household heads and rent payers. Secondary data sources, including books and internet resources, were utilized to supplement the primary data (Zikmund et al., 2010). The study population comprised occupants of rental residential properties in Rumuokwachi Community. The sampling frame included households occupying one-bedroom, two-bedroom, and three-bedroom apartments. A combination of ground truthing and simple random sampling techniques was employed to ensure unbiased respondent selection. Geographic Information System (GIS) mapping was used to delineate flooded areas within a one-kilometer radius, identifying 1,966 residential buildings. Slovin's formula was applied at a 5% precision level, yielding a sample size of 332 respondents. Data collection was facilitated through a structured questionnaire consisting of closed-ended questions for residents. The questionnaire covered causes of flooding, impact of floodings on property investments, and mitigation measures against urban flooding. The collected data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods through the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). A five-point Likert scale was employed to assess respondents' opinions on the study variables, with responses ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree.

5.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

5.1 Distributions and Retrieved Copies of Questionnaire

Table 5.1: Distributions and Retrieved Copies of Questionnaire

Detailed Rate	Response Distributed Copies	Retrieved Copies	Not-Retrieved Copies	Discarded Copies	Used Copies
Total	332(100%)	247(74.4%)	85(25.6%)	5(1.5%)	242(72.9%)

Source: Research Survey, 2024

Table 5.1 above illustrates the response rate of the questionnaires administered for this study. A total of 334 questionnaires were distributed, which represents 100% of the sample size. Out of the 334 questionnaires, 85 (25.6%) were not returned, and 5 (1.5%) were discarded due to errors in completion. This leaves 242 viable questionnaires, representing 72.9%, available for analysis.

5.1 Respondents' Demographic Profile

Demographics refer to quantifiable characteristics of a population and involve the study of factors such as age, gender, and marital status. In this study, the demographics examined included age, gender, and educational attainment. As shown in Figure 5.1, 113 respondents (46.7%) were male, while the majority, 129 respondents (53.3%), were female. This indicates that there were more female participants than males in the flood-affected Rumuokachi community of Rivers State.

Figure 5.1: Bar Chart showing the Gender Distribution for the Population

Source: Research Survey, 2024

Further, figure 5.2 below showed the age bracket of the respondents used for this study, the results demonstrates that most of the respondents were within the ages of 31-40 with a frequency of 98 representing (40.5%) of the population, this was followed by those aged between 41 - 50 as presented with a frequency of 76 representing 31.4% followed by respondents that are 20-30 years with a frequency of 45 that represents 18.6% of the population. Only 23 of the respondents representing 9.5% of the population are 51 years and above. The results indicated a higher number of respondents aged 31-40 and 41-50, suggesting that those who participated in the study were sufficiently mature and knowledgeable in this area of research.

Figure 5.2: Showing the bar chart on respondents' age distribution for the population

Source: Research Survey, 2024

Finally, figure 5.3 below showed the response rate for educational qualification in the study, out of the 242 that is (100%) copies of the questionnaire used for analysis, 23 representing (9.5%) of the respondents are SSCE/NCE holders 148 that is (61.2%) of the respondents are Bachelor's degree holders and its equivalent and the remaining 71 representing the (29.3%) of the respondents are post-

graduate degree holders. The various qualifications indicate that respondents were able to easily understand the topic under study.

Figure 5.3: Showed the bar chart on respondents’ education background for the population

Source: Research Survey, 2024

5.2 Response Rate on Causes of Flooding in Rumuokwachi Community

Table 5.2 contains the analysis of the causes of flooding in Rumuokwachi community in Rivers State from the perspectives of the residents. The table 5.2 shows that majority of the residents were of the opinion that rainfall is the major cause of flooding in the study area.

Table 5.2: Causes of Flooding in Rumuokwachi Community

Causes of Flooding in Rumuokwachi Community	SD	A	U	SD	D		Mean	SD
Drainage Problems	77	66	41	33	25	242	3.57	3.31
Sea Level Rise	95	54	47	24	22	242	3.73	3.45
Poor Refuse Disposal	93	60	44	33	12	242	3.78	3.47
Heavy Rainfall	122	75	23	13	11	244	4.16	3.79
Poor land use policy	56	45	90	29	22	242	3.35	3.05
Blockage of water ways	97	57	45	22	21	242	3.77	3.48
Building on flood plain	43	60	66	40	33	242	3.17	2.91
Rapid Urbanization and Unplanned Development	93	60	44	33	12	242	3.78	3.47

Source: Research Survey, 2024

The responses from participants in the study regarding eight items designed to assess property owners' reactions to the causes of flooding in the Rumuokwachi Community, detailed in Table 5.2, provide valuable insights. For the first item, which examines whether drainage problems contribute to flooding in the community, respondents largely agreed, resulting in a mean score of 3.57 and a standard deviation of 3.31. Similarly, item two investigates the impact of sea-level rise on flooding, with participants showing agreement reflected in a mean score of 3.73 and a standard deviation of 3.45.

Regarding item three, which explores whether poor refuse disposal contributes to flooding, respondents affirmed this assertion, shown by a mean score of 3.78 and a standard deviation of 3.47. Item four, which inquiries about the role of heavy rainfall in flooding, received strong agreement, resulting in a notably high mean score of 4.16 and a standard deviation of 3.79. Furthermore, responses to item five, which

examines the effect of poor land use policies on flooding, indicated agreement, evidenced by a mean score of 3.35 and a standard deviation of 3.05. In item six, participants confirmed that the blockage of waterways contributes to flooding, with a mean score of 3.77 and a standard deviation of 3.48. Additionally, item seven assesses whether building on floodplains leads to flooding, also indicating agreement, with a mean score of 3.17 and a standard deviation of 2.91. Lastly, responses to item eight, which examines whether rapid urbanization and unplanned development cause flooding, received strong affirmation from respondents, resulting in a mean score of 3.78 and a standard deviation of 3.47. These findings collectively highlight the key factors contributing to flooding in the Rumuokwachi Community, as perceived by the respondents.

5.3 Number of Hours Water remains on the Land before Receding

It was shown in table above that the most serious causes of flooding in Rumuokwachi is rainfall. This theme seeks to find out how long water remains on land for 1 hour to 7days before receding during flooding incidents. Table 5.3 provides the results of respondents’ responses.

Table 5.3: Duration that Water remains on the Land before Receding

Duration	Frequency	%
Less than 1 hour	5	2.1
Between 1 – 12 hours	12	5.0
Between 1-24 hours	75	31.0
Between 2-4days	127	52.5
Between 5–7days	23	9.5
Total	242	100

Source: Research Survey, 2024

Table 5.3 presents an analysis of the duration that water remains on the land before receding in Rumuokwachi, based on residents' perspectives. The data reveals that 52.5% of residents believe water stays on the land for 2 to 4 days before receding. Additionally, 31% indicated that water remains for 1 to 24 hours, while 9.5% reported a duration of 5 to 7 days. Only 5% and 2.1% of residents stated that water remains on the land for 1 to 12 hours and less than 1 hour, respectively. This suggests that water tends to remain on the land for extended periods before receding in the study area.

5.4 Response Rate of Impact of Flooding on Residential Property Investment

Table 5.4: Physical Impact of Flooding on Residential Property Investment

Impact of Flooding on Residential Property Investment	SD	A	U	SD	D	Sum	Mean	SD
Reduction in Property Values	93	60	44	33	12	242	3.78	3.47
Decreased Demand for Flood-Prone Properties	112	77	21	16	16	242	4.05	3.71
Lower Occupancy Rates	56	45	90	29	22	242	3.35	3.05
Increasing insurance costs,	97	57	45	22	21	242	3.77	3.48
Diminishing rental income,	66	60	43	40	33	242	3.36	3.13
Reduced Future Growth Potential	56	45	90	29	22	242	3.35	3.05
Disrupting development projects	99	59	41	22	21	242	3.80	3.51
Raising long-term sustainability concerns.	93	60	44	33	12	242	3.78	3.47

Source: Research Survey, 2024

Table 5.4 presents the response rates for functional implementation, measured across three items using mean and standard deviation. The first item examined whether flooding leads to a reduction in property values. Respondents affirmed this with a high mean value of 3.78 and a standard deviation of 3.47. Similarly, the second item assessed whether flooding decreases demand for flood-prone properties, with a mean value of 4.05 and a standard deviation of 3.71, indicating strong agreement among respondents.

Additionally, respondents agreed that flooding lowers occupancy rates, as shown by a mean value of 3.35 and a standard deviation of 3.05. The fourth item investigated whether flooding increases insurance costs in the Rumuokwachi Community, which respondents also supported, reflected in a mean score of 3.77 and a standard deviation of 3.48. Furthermore, the findings indicated that flooding diminishes rental income, with a mean score of 3.36 and a standard deviation of 3.13. Regarding the effect of urban flooding on future growth potential, respondents confirmed its negative impact, reflected in a mean score of 3.35 and a standard deviation of 3.05. The study also found that flooding can increase property prices, as evidenced by a mean score of 3.80 and a standard deviation of 3.51. Respondents indicated that flooding disrupts development projects, also reflected in a mean score of 3.80 and a standard deviation of 3.51. Finally, flooding was found to raise long-term sustainability concerns, confirmed by a mean score of 3.78 and a standard deviation of 3.47. These findings underscore the significant impact of flooding on residential property investment in the Rumuokwachi Community, Rivers State.

5.5 Response Rate of Mitigation Measures against Reoccurrence of Urban Flooding

Table 5.5: Mitigation Measures against Flooding

Mitigation Measures against urban flooding to safe guard investment opportunities	SD	A	U	SD	D	Sum	Mean	SD
Flood Protection Embankments	93	60	44	33	12	242	3.78	3.47
Raising of Public Awareness through Better Education	112	77	21	16	16	242	4.05	3.71
Investing in Green Infrastructure	41	56	66	45	34	242	3.10	2.86
The Involvement of Communities in Planning Flood Control	98	87	26	16	15	242	3.98	3.63
Proper Zoning and Land-Use Policies	56	48	77	39	22	242	3.32	3.04
Creation of Drainage Network	45	45	97	24	31	242	3.20	2.92
Diversification into Non-Flood-Prone Areas	43	66	61	40	33	243	3.19	2.94
Flood Insurance	56	90	16	29	22	213	3.61	3.32
Urban renewal projects that target flood-prone	56	48	77	39	22	242	3.32	3.04

Source: Research Survey, 2024

Table 5.5 displays the response rates for various suggested mitigation measures against flooding, based on the mean and standard deviation across eight different items. The first item examined the effectiveness of flood protection embankments in preventing recurring flooding. This measure received a high mean value of 3.78, with a standard deviation of 3.47. Similarly, increasing public awareness through improved education was also recognized as an effective strategy, achieving a mean value of 4.05 and a standard deviation of 3.71. The third item assessed the potential benefits of investing in green infrastructure as a flood mitigation strategy. This approach received a mean value of 3.10 and a standard deviation of 2.86. Additionally, community involvement in flood control planning was strongly supported, reflected by a mean score of 3.98 and a standard deviation of 3.63. Proper zoning and land-use policies were identified as another effective Mitigation strategy, supported by a mean score of 3.32 and a standard deviation of 3.04. Likewise, diversifying activities into non-flood-prone areas was affirmed as a valuable measure, with a mean value of 3.20 and a standard deviation of 2.92. The desilting of drainage systems was also recognized as a viable approach, achieving a mean score of 3.19 and a standard deviation of 2.94. Furthermore, flood insurance was acknowledged as a critical mitigation strategy, with respondents affirming its importance through a mean value of 3.61 and a standard deviation of 3.32. Lastly, urban renewal projects targeting flood-prone areas were identified as a viable solution, obtaining a mean score of 3.32 and a standard deviation of 3.04. These findings underscore key

measures that could be implemented to mitigate the impact of flooding in the Rumuokwachi Community.

6.0 DISCUSSION AND INTERPRETATION OF FINDINGS

6.1 Causes of Flooding in Rumuokwachi Community

The findings from Table 5.2 reveal that rainfall is perceived as the primary cause of flooding in the Rumuokwachi Community. This aligns with the broader understanding that excessive rainfall contributes significantly to urban flooding, particularly in areas with inadequate drainage systems. The study further highlights other key factors, including drainage problems (mean = 3.57), sea-level rise (mean = 3.73), poor refuse disposal (mean = 3.78), and blockage of waterways (mean = 3.77), all of which exacerbate flooding incidents.

Notably, poor land-use policies (mean = 3.35) and rapid urbanization (mean = 3.78) were also identified as significant contributors to flooding. This finding underscores the role of unregulated urban expansion and improper zoning in increasing flood risks. Furthermore, respondents confirmed that constructing buildings on floodplains (mean = 3.17) worsens the situation by obstructing natural water flow paths. These results align with previous research emphasizing the interplay between environmental, infrastructural, and human-induced factors in flood occurrences (Adelekan, 2012; Odemerho, 2015).

6.2 Duration of Floodwater Retention in Rumuokwachi

Table 5.3 indicates that floodwaters in Rumuokwachi tend to persist for extended periods before receding. Over half of the respondents (52.5%) reported that floodwater remains on land for 2 to 4 days, while 31% noted durations ranging from 1 to 24 hours. This prolonged retention of floodwater is a critical issue, as it can lead to severe infrastructural damage, increased health risks due to stagnant water, and reduced property usability.

These findings suggest that poor drainage infrastructure and inadequate flood control mechanisms contribute to water stagnation. The prolonged presence of water highlights the need for urgent interventions to improve drainage capacity and enhance flood resilience in the community.

6.3 Impact of Flooding on Residential Property Investment

The results in Table 5.4 indicate that flooding has significant negative implications for residential property investments in Rumuokwachi. Key impacts include a reduction in property values (mean = 3.78), decreased demand for flood-prone properties (mean = 4.05), and lower occupancy rates (mean = 3.35). These findings align with global trends, where frequent flooding leads to declining real estate market confidence in affected areas (Filatova et al., 2019). Additionally, the study found that flooding increases insurance costs (mean = 3.77) and diminishes rental income (mean = 3.36), making property investments in flood-prone areas less attractive. Notably, flooding was also associated with disrupting development projects (mean = 3.80) and raising long-term sustainability concerns (mean = 3.78). These findings suggest that investors may become hesitant to commit to real estate developments in the area unless effective mitigation strategies are implemented. Interestingly, respondents also indicated that flooding could increase property prices (mean = 3.80). This may be due to speculative investments where land scarcity drives up prices despite flood risks. However, in the long term, sustained flooding events are more likely to deter investment and lead to economic losses.

6.4 Mitigation Measures Against Flooding

The results in Table 5.5 highlight various strategies that could mitigate flooding in Rumuokwachi. Respondents strongly affirmed the effectiveness of flood protection embankments (mean = 3.78) and public awareness campaigns (mean = 4.05) in reducing flood risks. This aligns with global best practices where structural interventions and public education play crucial roles in flood disaster management (IPCC, 2014). The study also identified green infrastructure (mean = 3.10) and community involvement in flood control planning (mean = 3.98) as viable strategies. Proper zoning and land-use policies (mean = 3.32) were acknowledged as essential in reducing flood vulnerability, further reinforcing the need for stringent regulatory frameworks. Other recommended strategies include diversifying investments into non-flood-prone areas (mean = 3.20), desilting drainage systems (mean = 3.19), and promoting flood insurance (mean = 3.61). Urban renewal projects targeting flood-prone areas (mean = 3.32) were also

recognized as an important long-term measure. These findings indicate that a multi-faceted approach, combining infrastructural improvements, policy interventions, and community engagement, is required to mitigate the adverse effects of flooding in Rumuokwachi. The study underscores that flooding in Rumuokwachi is primarily driven by excessive rainfall, poor drainage systems, and unregulated urbanization. The prolonged retention of floodwater exacerbates property investment risks, leading to declining property values, reduced demand, and increased insurance costs. However, implementing effective mitigation strategies such as flood embankments, improved zoning policies, and public awareness campaigns could help address these challenges.

7.0 CONCLUSION

The findings of this study emphasize the significant impact of flooding on the Rumuokwachi Community, revealing that excessive rainfall, poor drainage infrastructure, and unregulated urbanization are the primary causes of recurring flood events. The prolonged retention of floodwater further exacerbates the negative effects, contributing to declining property values, reduced demand for real estate in flood-prone areas, increased insurance costs, and disruptions to property development projects. These challenges highlight the vulnerability of residential property investments in flood-prone communities. Despite these challenges, the study identifies several effective mitigation strategies. Structural interventions, such as flood protection embankments and improved drainage systems, alongside non-structural measures, such as public awareness campaigns, community involvement in flood control planning, and proper zoning regulations, were recognized as viable solutions. Additionally, diversification into non-flood-prone areas, investment in green infrastructure, desilting of drainage systems, and urban renewal projects targeting flood-prone areas emerged as key recommendations for reducing the adverse effects of flooding. To enhance resilience against flooding, it is imperative for policymakers, urban planners, and real estate stakeholders to adopt a multi-faceted approach that integrates regulatory reforms, infrastructural improvements, and community-driven initiatives. Future research could explore the cost-benefit analysis of implementing these mitigation strategies to inform evidence-based decision-making and sustainable flood management practices. Addressing the root causes of flooding in Rumuokwachi through proactive policies and targeted interventions will not only safeguard property investments but also improve the overall livability and sustainability of the community.

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